

Intraperitoneal and Port Site Infiltration of Ropivacaine With and Without Dexmedetomidine for Postoperative Analgesia After Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy: A Randomised Controlled Trial

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ABSTRACT

Use of intraperitoneal and port site infiltration of local anaesthetics has been used to reduce postoperative pain and need for different analgesic agents delivered from various routes following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Ropivacaine and highly selective alpha 2-agonist dexmedetomidine are the newer agents which are being increasingly used for peri-operative analgesia. The present study compared intraperitoneal and port site infiltration of ropivacaine and dexmedetomidine for postoperative analgesia in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Sixty patients scheduled for laparoscopic cholecystectomy were enrolled in this prospective randomized double blind controlled study and assigned to 2 groups ($n = 30$) to receive either 40 ml of 0.25% ropivacaine with 2 ml of normal (Group R) or 40 ml of 0.25% ropivacaine combined with 1 µg/kg dexmedetomidine diluted in normal saline to 2 ml (Group RD) infiltrated intraperitoneally and at port site after gall bladder removal following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Haemodynamic parameters, Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) score for pain assessment, total duration of analgesia, total requirement of analgesic in first 24 hours were recorded. Data obtained were compiled and analyzed with appropriate tests. A value of < 0.05 was considered significant. Total duration of postoperative analgesia was higher in Group RD whereas, VAS score and total rescue analgesic requirement were significantly lower as compare to group R. There was no significant difference in haemodynamic parameters between the groups. The addition of dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant along with ropivacaine for intraperitoneal and port site infiltration is an effective method of postoperative pain relief following laparoscopic cholecystectomy without significant adverse effects.

KEY WORDS: dexmedetomidine, intraperitoneal infiltration, laparoscopic cholecystectomy, port site infiltration, postoperative analgesia, ropivacaine

INTRODUCTION:

Postoperative pain is a self-limiting phenomenon but a pain free postoperative phase increases patient's co-operation and activity levels, leading to early recovery.^[1] Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy is one of the most frequently performed elective surgical procedure due to its numerous advantages like minimal tissue trauma, lesser bleeding and pain, shorter recovery time and

decreased hospital stay thereby, leading to overall reduced healthcare costs.^[3]

The components of pain following laparoscopic cholecystectomy include visceral pain due to peritoneal inflammation resulting from release of inflammatory mediators and stretching of the intra-abdominal cavity. Shoulder pain results from irritation of phrenic nerve endings present in the diaphragm due to over-stretching caused by pneumoperitoneum. Parietal pain is due to surgical incision for the insertion of laparoscopic ports which is much lesser in intensity by virtue of its smaller size.^[5] The major component of pain is attributed to visceral pain with maximal intensity during the first 24 hours postoperatively and is exacerbated by coughing, respiratory movements and mobilization.^[6]

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Multimodal strategies for analgesia including infiltration of wound with local anaesthetics, administration of systemic narcotics and NSAIDs, intravenous and epidural patient controlled analgesia (PCA) with different class of analgesics and local anaesthetics enhance pain relief and reduce the side effects in postoperative period.^[7,8,9]

Local anesthetics have been used intraperitoneally since 1950 as they are known to block the visceral afferent receptors signaling to the brain and potentially modify their conduction, thereby providing analgesia.^[10,11,12] They also inhibit nociception through their action on nerve membrane associated proteins, inhibiting the release of prostaglandins and lysosomal enzymes along with leukocyte migration. The main advantage of using intraperitoneal route is that it does not have the adverse effects as of systemically administered drugs such as postoperative sedation, nausea and respiratory suppression because they act directly on the affected tissue. Recently, a variety of non-opioid adjuvant have been used clinically to speed up the onset and increase the duration of sensory and motor blockade.

The present study aimed at comparing ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine and ropivacaine as agents for pain relief by intraperitoneal and post site infiltration of local anesthetics in patients after laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The aim of the study was to determine the duration of postoperative analgesia of 0.25% ropivacaine with and without dexmedetomidine (1µg/kg) after intraperitoneal instillation in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Hemodynamic changes, need of rescue analgesics and any side effects or complications were also recorded and compared.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

After institutional ethical committee (IEC) approval, this prospective, randomized, double-blind study was conducted among 60 patients of ASA physical status I and II between age group 18–65 years of either gender scheduled for laparoscopic cholecystectomy under general anesthesia in BPSGMC (W), Khanpur, Kalan Sonapat, Haryana.

Cases with morbid obesity, significant systemic illness, known allergy to drugs under study, pregnant and lactating women, chronic pain syndrome and coagulation disorders, previous abdominal surgery, intra-abdominal drain placement postoperatively and refusal to participate were excluded from the study.

Based on our pilot study, taking a difference in

duration of postoperative pain relief of 2 hrs between the two groups as clinically significant, to have an 80% power in present study with 95% confidence interval, 30 cases were recruited in each study group. A total of 60 patients were randomly divided into two groups of 30 each using computer generated simple random number table to receive either 40 ml of 0.25% ropivacaine with 2 ml of normal saline (Group R) or 40 ml of 0.25% ropivacaine plus 1µg/kg dexmedetomidine diluted to 2 ml with normal saline (Group RD).

Data was recorded in pretested performa meeting the objectives of the study. Pre-anaesthetic check-up (PAC) was done for each patient and written informed consent was taken. On arrival to the operating room, routine ASA standard monitors were attached. Baseline vital parameters were recorded prior to premedication, at every 5-minutes interval from the start of induction for first 30 minutes and then at every 10 minutes interval till the end of surgery.

Surgery was carried out under general anaesthesia with standard four trocar technique after pre-medicating with midazolam (0.04mg/kg), ondansetran (0.1mg/kg) and glycopyrrolate (4µg/kg) intravenously. A standard technique of general anaesthesia was followed for all the patients among both the groups. Pre-oxygenation with 100% oxygen was done for 3 minutes. Induction of anaesthesia was done with i.v. fentanyl (2 µg/kg) and propofol (2 mg/kg) followed by vecuronium bromide (0.12 mg/kg). The airway was secured using appropriate sized supraglottic airway device or with cuffed orotracheal tube of appropriate size and thereafter, nasogastric tube was inserted. Anaesthesia was maintained with 50% N₂O in oxygen with sevoflurane. Intermittent boluses of i.v. vecuronium bromide (0.02 mg/kg) were given to maintain neuromuscular blockade. Minute ventilation was adjusted to maintain end tidal carbon-dioxide [EtCO₂] 40 ± 5 mmHg. Patients were placed in 15-20° reverse Trendelenburg's position. During laparoscopy, intra-abdominal pressure was maintained at 10-12 mmHg. The study drug was prepared by the first investigator who was aware of group allocation of the cases and not involved in the study. The second investigator was unaware of the drug solution prepared by the first investigator and provided the surgeon with the drug for instillation and observed the patient until the end of study. At the end of surgery, a total of 32 ml of study drug solution was instilled intraperitoneally after peritoneal wash and suctioning, before removal of trocar (16 ml of solution was splayed over right

subdiaphragmatic space and another 16 ml in gall bladder fossa via epigastric port site) in Trendelenburg's position (15-20°). The remaining 10 ml of drug solution was infiltrated at trocar insertion sites after removal of trocar. Patients were kept in same position for 10 minutes to facilitate the dispersion of the drug solution at desired site.

Residual muscle paralysis was reversed with i.v. neostigmine (0.05mg/kg) and glycopyrrolate (0.01mg/kg). After suctioning, the nasogastric tube was removed and once the criteria for extubation was fulfilled, the airway device was also removed. In the post-anaesthesia care unit (PACU) no analgesic supplement was given till the patient complained of pain (VAS score <3). Diclofenac sodium 1.5mg/kg was given intravenously as first line rescue analgesic if patient had VAS score >3 and i.v. tramadol 1 mg/kg was administered to any patient who still had VAS score >3 after 20 min of administration of first line analgesic.

Postoperatively, patients were assessed at 0-hour interval (immediate postoperative period), 1-hour interval (in the recovery room) and at the time when VAS>3 or at the time of demand for first analgesic for intensity of pain (irrespective of location and type of pain) utilizing VAS along with haemodynamic parameters (HR, SBP, DBP, MBP). The total analgesic consumption in the first 24 hours postoperatively was also calculated. The patients were monitored for side effects and complications of technique and drugs throughout intraoperative and postoperative period in both the groups, if any.

The data was entered in Microsoft Excel spread sheet and analyzed using SPSS software version 22. For quantitative data mean $\pm$ SD was calculated. For qualitative data chi-square test was used and percentage was calculated. For qualitative data repeated measure ANOVA and Post-Hoc Bonferroni test was used to find out mean difference between two groups. p-value <0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS:

In the present study, both the groups were comparable with respect to mean age, sex, weight of the patients, and ASA distribution (Table 1). Comparison of intraoperative haemodynamic parameters (mean HR, SBP, DBP, MBP, SpO₂ and EtCO₂) did not reveal any statistically significant difference amongst both the groups.

The haemodynamic parameters (HR, SBP, DBP, and MBP and SpO₂) were recorded postoperatively in both the groups at 0-hr, 1-hr, at the hour when

Table 1: Demographic distribution amongst the study groups

Variable	Group	Mean	SD	p-value
Age (years)	R	35.73	±10.68	0.561
	RD	34.20	±9.61	
Weight (kg)	R	55.93	±8.94	0.551
	RD	55.77	±5.77	
Height (cm)	R	154.83	±5.77	0.609
	RD	154.17	±4.08	
BMI (kg/m ²)	R	23.5	±3.28	0.491
	RD	23.08	±2.08	

VAS>3 or at the demand for first analgesic dose and found to be statistically insignificant.

The mean VAS score was recorded at defined time intervals and found to be lower in Group RD in comparison to Group R. The mean VAS score reading at 1-hour was statistically significant with $p = 0.043$, (Table 2).

Mean time for first rescue analgesic and the total duration of analgesia were significantly higher in cases administered with ropivacaine and dexmedetomidine as compared to ropivacaine alone with difference being statistically significant (p-value <0.001). Mean dose of rescue analgesic required was also higher in R group (p<0.001) (Graph 1).

Complications were noted in <20% of the patients in both the groups which were managed conservatively with no other life threatening adverse effects (Graph 2).

DISCUSSION:

Numerous studies available in literature have compared either one of the commonly used local anaesthetics like bupivacaine, lignocaine with a placebo such as normal saline or with different concentrations of same local anaesthetics.

Ropivacaine in a concentration of 0.25% was chosen for this trial as higher concentrations of drug like 0.50% and 0.75% had already been studied extensively and concluded that lower concentration is equally effective for providing postoperative analgesia when compared to higher drug concentrations^[13,14]. Babu R et al. conducted a study including 60

Table 2: Comparison of mean VAS in the postoperative period amongst the study groups.

Time Interval	Group R (Mean ± SD)	Group RD (Mean ± SD)	p-value
0-hour	0.80±0.61	0.73±0.52	0.651
1-hour	1.72±0.34	1.53±0.37	0.043
Time for VAS>3	3.86±0.51	3.86±0.51	1.00

Table 3: Mean time for first rescue, and total number of rescue analgesics in 24 hours.

	Group	Mean±SD	Median	p-value
Duration of analgesia (min)	R	86.60±28.76	91.00	<0.001
	RD	416.20±127.36	454.50	
Total analgesic requirement(mg)	R	182.50±37.80	150.00	<0.001
	RD	87.50±39.80	75.00	

Graph 1: Bar diagram for comparison of Mean time for first rescue analgesic and total dose of rescue analgesia required in 1st 24 hour.

Graph 2: Bar diagram showing incidence of postoperative complications amongst the groups

patients for evaluation of postoperative analgesia following laparoscopic cholecystectomy after intraperitoneal instillation of 0.2% ropivacaine and 0.25% bupivacaine. It was concluded that both ropivacaine and bupivacaine are equally effective as postoperative analgesics but ropivacaine has better cardiac safety profile and is an attractive alternate to the bupivacaine^[15].

Also, the volume of the drug solution selected for our study was 42 ml as many studies had already been conducted with higher volume of drug solutions like 50 ml, 75 ml, 100 ml and even up to 500 ml.^[16] In a study conducted by Shivhare P, et al 30 ml of 0.5% ropivacaine and normal saline each was given to see the effect of intraperitoneal instillation of ropivacaine on postoperative abdominal and shoulder pain. Intraperitoneal instillation of ropivacaine was found to be an effective method of postoperative pain relief in laparoscopic cholecystectomy with such a low volume of drug solution which in consonance with our study^[17]. In a study conducted by Jain S, et al. peritoneal cavity was irrigated with 500 ml of drug solutions for postoperative analgesia in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. It was found that high-volume low-concentration of intraperitoneal bupivacaine significantly increases postoperative duration of analgesia and reduces opioid requirement after laparoscopic cholecystectomy. However, the volume of the drug solution chosen for the study was comparatively higher and is in discordance with our study^[16].

We used the intraperitoneal instillation of drug solution at the end of the procedure in the trendelenburg position with trocars intact along with infiltration of drug solution at the port site^[18,19]. This dual technique of providing analgesia covers not only visceral pain arising from the gall bladder fossa but also parietal pain arising from the surgical trauma to abdominal wall. This avoids any bias in evaluation of pain and is also more comforting to the patient. Trendelenburg position aids in the flow and accumulation of drug solution over the coeliac plexus and free nerve endings leading to improved pain relief by blocking the nociceptive impulses.

All the haemodynamic parameters like mean heart rate, mean SBP, mean DBP, mean MAP, mean SpO₂ and mean EtCo₂ amongst both the study groups were comparable at the baseline, during intraoperative and the post operative period (p value>0.05). The results of our study are comparable to the study done by Meena R, et al comparing the efficacy of intraperitoneal infiltration of 0.5% bupivacaine and

0.75% ropivacaine to reduce postoperative pain in the patients with laparoscopic cholecystectomy. No significant difference (p>0.05) in haemodynamic characteristics were observed in concordance with our present study^[20]. Similar findings were observed in the studies conducted by Sharan R, et al, Singh A et al^[21,22].

In our study, mean VAS score was compared at 0-hour (immediate postoperative period), 1-hour postoperatively and at the hour when patient demanded of analgesia or VAS >3. The mean value of VAS score was overall low at 0-hour among both the groups and was statistically insignificant (p-value>0.05). Mean VAS score at 1-hour postoperatively was significantly lower among group RD as compared to the group R (1.53±0.37 v/s 1.72±0.34). When the mean VAS score was >3 and the patient complained of pain they were administered with rescue analgesics as per protocol. So, the next recordings of VAS were comparable as these were recorded at different time intervals. These results are comparable to the studies done by Chiruvella S, Babu R and Oza VP^[23, 14 & 24], which also recorded reduction in mean VAS in 24 hours.

But on contrary Gurusamy KS found that there was very low quality evidence that it reduces pain in low anaesthetic risk patients undergoing elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy^[25].

The mean total duration of analgesia was significantly higher in cases administered with ropivacaine and dexmedetomidine as compared to ropivacaine alone group (416.20 min v/s 86.60 min; p-value <0.01) whereas, cumulative requirement of rescue analgesics in the postoperative period was lower in first 24 hour (182.50 mg v/s 87.50 mg; p-value<0.01) (Table 3). Our results are in congruence with studies done by Chiruvella S, Shukla U and Singh A,^[23, 26 & 22] which also showed significantly better analgesic effect of dexmedetomidine when added to local anaesthetic solution.

In our study complications were noted in less than 20% of the patients among both the groups. Nausea and vomiting was observed in 5 patients of Group R and 6 patients of Group RD. Shoulder pain was observed in 2 patients among group R and RD. There was no episode of hypotension, bradycardia, arrhythmia, sedation, respiratory depression and any other life threatening side effects among both the groups. All the readings were comparable and the difference was found to be non significant in the two groups (p value>0.05).

The results were also in concordance with Singh A, Shukla U and Meena R observed no

statistically significant difference in regard to the adverse effects amongst the study groups ($p > 0.05$)^[22,26 & 20]

CONCLUSION:

Our study concluded that combination of ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine when administered intraperitoneally and infiltrated at port site is an effective and reliable technique for postoperative pain management in the patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy under general anaesthesia. It not only reduces cumulative dose of rescue analgesics in the first 24 hours postoperatively but also improves the quality of analgesia. Moreover, this technique is not associated with any major adverse effects and may be incorporated in routine anaesthesia practice for providing postoperative analgesia in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

REFERENCES:

1. Kehlet H. Post operative pain relief-what is the issue? *Br J Anaesth.* 1994; 72:375-8.
2. Bisgaard T, Kehlet H, Rosenberg J. Pain and convalescence after laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Eur J Korean Surg Soc.* 2010;79:130-6.
3. Manne GR, Upadhyaya MR, Swadia VN. Effects of low dose dexmedetomidine infusion on haemodynamic stress response, sedation and Postoperative analgesia requirement in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Ind J Anaesth.* 2014; 58: 726-31.
4. Bina P, Butala, Veena R, Shah, K, Nived. Randomized double blind trial of intraperitoneal instillation of bupivacaine and morphine for pain relief after laparoscopic gynecological surgeries. *Saudi J Anaesth.* 2013; 7(1): 18–23.
5. Møiniche S, Jørgensen H, Wetterslev J, Dahl JB. Local anaesthetic infiltration for postoperative pain relief after laparoscopy: A qualitative and quantitative systematic review of intraperitoneal, port site infiltration and mesosalpinx block. *Anesth Analg.* 2000;90:899-912.
6. Rees BI, Williams HR. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy the first 155 patients. *Am R Coll Surg Engl.* 1992; 74: 233-6.
7. Scott AND, Greville AC, Mc Millan L, Wellwood J, Mc K. Laparoscopic laser cholecystectomy results of the technique in 210 patients. *Am R coll Surg Engl.* 1992; 74: 237-41.
8. Lord Mc Coll. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Am R Coll Surg Engl.* 1992; 74: 231.
9. Hanson IR, Hingson RA. The use of xylocaine, a new local anaesthetic, in surgery, obstetrics and therapeutics. *Curr Res Anesth Analg.* 1950;29: 136–47.
10. Newcomb W, Lincourt A, Hope W, Schmelzer T, Sing R, Kercher K, et al. Prospective, double-blinded, randomized, placebo-controlled comparison of local anesthetic and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs for postoperative pain management after laparoscopic surgery. *Am Surg.* 2007;73:618–24.
11. Griffin EM, Prystowsky H, Hingson RA. The use of topical anaesthesia of the peritoneum in poor risk surgery and in augmenting inadequate vertebral conduction anaesthesia. *st Z Med J.* 1951;50:31–3.
12. McClure JH. Ropivacaine. *Brit J Anaesth.* 1996;76: 300-307.
13. Kuthiala G, Chaudhary G. Ropivacaine: A review of its pharmacology and clinical use. *Indian J Anaesth.* 2011; 55(2): 104–110
14. Babu R, Jain P, Sherif L. Intraperitoneal instillation: Ropivacaine vs Bupivacaine for postoperative pain relief in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Int J Health Sci Res.* 2013;3(12):42-7
15. Jain S, Nazir N, Singh S, Sharma S. A prospective randomized controlled study for evaluation of High-volume low-concentration of intraperitoneal bupivacaine for post-laparoscopic cholecystectomy analgesia. *Indian J Anaesth* 2018;62:109-14.
16. Shivhare P, Dugg P, Singh H, Mittal S, Kumar A, Munghate A. A prospective randomized trial to study the effect of intraperitoneal instillation of ropivacaine in postoperative pain reduction in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *J Minim Invasive Surg Sci.* 2014; 3(4):e18009.
17. Putta PG, Pasupuleti H, Samantaray A, Natham H, Rao MH. A comparative evaluation of pre-emptive versus post-surgery intraperitoneal local anaesthetic instillation for postoperative pain relief after laparoscopic cholecystectomy: A prospective, randomised, double blind and placebo controlled study. *Indian J Anaesth.* 2019;63(3):205–211.
18. Lee IO, Kim SH, Kong MH, Lee MK, Kim NS, Choi YS, et al. Pain after laparoscopic cholecystectomy: The effect and timing of incisional and intraperitoneal bupivacaine. *Can J Anaesth.* 2001;48:545–50.
19. Meena R, Meena K, Loha S, Prakash S. A comparative study of intraperitoneal Ropivacaine and Bupivacaine for postoperative analgesia in laparoscopic cholecystectomy: a randomized controlled trial. *Anaesth Pain & Intensive Care* 2016;20(3):295-30.
20. Sharan R, Singh M, Kataria AP, Jyoti K, Jarewal V, Kadian R. Intraperitoneal instillation of bupivacaine and ropivacaine for postoperative analgesia in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Anesth Essays Res* 2018;12:377-80.
21. Singh A, Mathur SK, Shukla VK. Postoperative analgesia with intraperitoneal ropivacaine with and without fentanyl after laparoscopic cholecystectomy: A randomized double-blind controlled trial. *OA Anaesthetics* 2013 May 01;1(1):9.
22. Sunil Chiruvella, Srinivasa Rao Nallam. Intraperitoneal instillation of ropivacaine plus dexmedetomi-

- dine for pain relief after laparoscopic hysterectomy: A comparison with ropivacaine alone. *J NTR Univ Health Sci* 2016;5:93-7.
23. Oza VP, Parmar V, Badheka J, Nanavati DS, Taur P, Rajyaguru AM. Comparative study of postoperative analgesic effect of intraperitoneal instillation of dexmedetomidine with bupivacaine and bupivacaine alone after laparoscopic surgery. *J Min Access Surg* 2016;12:2.
 24. Gurusamy KS, Nagendran M, Guerrini GP et al. Intraperitoneal local anaesthetic instillation versus no intraperitoneal local anaesthetic instillation for laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2014; (3): CD007337.
 25. Shukla U, Prabhakar T, Malhotra K, Srivastava D, Malhotra K. Intraperitoneal Bupivacaine alone or with dexmedetomidine or tramadol for Postoperative analgesia following laparoscopic cholecystectomy: A comparative evaluation. *Indian J Anaesth*. 2015;59: 234-9.

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